

Sample 35a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0001
{Si}	82.7
{Al, Si}	4.9
{Si, Ca LoP}	2.1
{Na, Al, Si}	2.0
{Al, Si, K}	1.8
{Ca}	1.8
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.0
{Si, Ca HiP}	0.7
{Fe}	0.5
{Si, K}	0.5
{Na, Si}	0.5
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
{Mg, Si}	0.2
{Si, Fe}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
{Mg, Ca}	0.1
{Si, P}	0.1
{S}	0.0
{Si, Fe}	0.0
{Al}	0.0
{Si, S, Ca}	0.0
{P, Ca}	0.0
{Si, P, Ca}	0.0
{Ti}	0.0
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0
{Na, Al, Si, S}	0.0
{S, Ca}	0.0
{P}	0.0
{Al, Si, S}	0.0
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
{Na, Al, Si, K}	0.0
{Na, Mg, Si, Cl}	0.0
{Mg, Si, Cl}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.1
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.1
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	8.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
Carbon rich - other	1.6
Cement or BOF converter	0.2
Cement	9.8
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	77.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	0.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.2
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	1.2
Site - slag; urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.1
Site - flux / slag; + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	8.8
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.6
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.2
Urban	9.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	77.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	0.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 35b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0001
{Si}	84.7
{Al, Si}	4.6
{Al, Si, K}	2.6
{Si, Ca LoP}	1.6
{Na, Al, Si}	1.4
{Ca}	1.3
{Si, K}	0.6
{Si, Ca HiP}	0.6
{Na, Si}	0.6
{Al, Si, Ca}	0.5
{Fe}	0.3
{Si, P}	0.3
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Si, Fe}	0.1
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Mg, Si}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
{Si, S, Ca}	0.0
{S}	0.0
{Si, Fe}	0.0
{S, Ca}	0.0
{Al, Ca}	0.0
{Al}	0.0
{Si, P, Ca}	0.0
{Na, Al, Si, K}	0.0
{Ti}	0.0
{P, Ca}	0.0
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0
{Na, Al, Si, S}	0.0
{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.0
{Mg, Fe}	0.0
{Al, Si, S}	0.0
{P}	0.0
{S, K}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.4
Desulph slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	6.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.4
Carbon rich - other	0.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	87.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	0.8
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.4

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	2.0
Site - slag; urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag; + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	6.8
Site - carbon-rich other	0.4
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	0.4
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	0.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	87.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	0.8
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.4

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 35c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0000
{Si}	76.1
{Al, Si}	6.8
{Si, Ca LoP}	3.9
{Na, Al, Si}	2.9
{Ca}	2.3
{Al, Si, K}	2.2
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.2
{Fe}	0.9
{Si, Ca HIP}	0.8
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
{Na, Si}	0.5
{Si, K}	0.4
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Si, Fe}	0.2
{Mg, Si}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
{Al}	0.0
{Si, S, Ca}	0.0
{Si, Fe}	0.0
{Si, P}	0.0
{S, Ca}	0.0
{P, Ca}	0.0
{Si, P, Ca}	0.0
{P, Fe}	0.0
{Ca, Fe}	0.0
{Ti}	0.0
{Na, Al, Si, S}	0.0
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0
{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.0
{Al, Ca}	0.0
{Al, Si, S}	0.0
{Mg, Ca}	0.0
{P}	0.0
{Na, Al, Si, K}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	1.5
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.6
Desulph slag	0.7
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	9.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.6
Carbon rich - other	1.8
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	5.8
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	76.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	0.1
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.7
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	4.8
Site - slag; urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.1
Site - flux / slag; + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	9.5
Site - carbon-rich other	0.6
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.8
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	5.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	76.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	0.1
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels